

20 years of Open Access publishing initiatives: A bibliometric analysis in the Insular Caribbean Region

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Abstract

In the early 2000s attendees of a meeting in Budapest drafted the first formal declaration advocating Open Access to scientific and scholarly literature. After that, there have been many other discussions, declarations and key initiatives on Open Access to research publications around the world. Despite the Open Access movement is now over twenty years old and growing interest to remove barriers to peer-reviewed scholarly literature, there is not up-to-date and reproducible studies assessing the prevalence and characteristics of Open Access specifically in the Insular Caribbean Region. The purpose of this study is to trace outgrowth and development of Open Access in this region over the last two decades. The bibliographic data collected was extracted from Scopus. We elaborated indicators related about variants of Open Access types, publication year of the Open Access documents, country of publication, languages, and subject areas. The findings disclosed that the Open Access publishing is increasingly in the region and the golden route has experienced greater advances. Cuba and Puerto Rico stand out with the highest open production. We hope our analysis might serve as a basis for scientific institutions of the region to implement policies and initiatives supporting Open Access models of scientific communication.

Introduction

The scholarly communication landscape has changed profoundly over the past two decades. One of significant landmarks was the meeting called by the Open Society Institute (OSI) and held at Budapest in 2001, in which the first document mentioning the expression “Open Access (OA)” was produced (BOAI - Budapest Open Access Initiative 2002). Subsequently, Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing came out in April 2003 in Maryland/ USA with the purpose of initiating discussions on how to provide Open Access to the primary scientific literature in biomedical research; and October of that same year was published the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities. After these initiatives, many countries, funding agencies, and institutions have formulated policies to promote the development of OA (Costa & Leite, 2016). This new publishing model for scholarly communication makes research information available to readers at no cost, as opposed to the traditional subscription model in which readers have access to scholarly information by paying a subscription (usually via libraries). Since then, we observed a profusion of new publishing and subscription models from commercial and not-for-profit publishers.

Despite the movement to provide OA to all research literature is now over twenty years old and the interest in OA to scholarly literature is growing, there is not up-to-date and reproducible studies assessing the prevalence and characteristics of OA specifically in the Insular Caribbean Region. Possibly because it is a subregion of the American continent made up of a complex geopolitical system including sovereign states and overseas territories (Figure 1) falling under the jurisdiction of the larger wealthy developed nations of France, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and the USA as well sovereign states, it has not been sufficiently explored in regional science studies. Many researchers have estimated what proportion of the literature is available OA, but mostly bibliometric studies include the Latin American region, which is formed by an extensive numerous of countries, varying greatly in size and population (Babini, 2011; Appel, Lujano & Albagli, 2018; Fernández Eysseric & Murillo González (2019); León

González, 2020). Although there is in the region a notable group of higher education institutions, almost never all Caribbean Insular countries are considered (for example: Lesser Antilles and the small islands in the northern Caribbean).

Figure 1. Map of the Insular Caribbean displaying island size and geographic shape
Source: López-Marrero, Heartsill Scalley & Villanueva Colón (2012)

The purpose of this study is to trace outgrowth and development of OA in the Insular Caribbean Region. After 20 years that the concept of “Open Access” was coined and formally defined, we pretend, first, describe how Insular Caribbean Region is moving forward in widening access to OA and, second, investigate the directions and trends of these OA publications. Given the access to scholarly literature is at the heart of current debates in the research community and the perspective is timely for countries socially and historically excluded from the center of science (Costa & Leite, 2016), we would like to answer the following questions:

- What types of OA are most common in the Insular Caribbean Region?
- How does OA vary by year of publication and across disciplines in the region countries?

This article is a product of the research in progress about “Open Science in the Caribbean Region” that takes place at the Unit for Monitoring and Analysis of Scientific Research in Puerto Rico (UMAIPUR, 2022). We hope our analysis might serve as a basis for scientific institutions of the region to implement policies and initiatives supporting OA models of scientific communication.

Sources and methodology

We conducted a bibliometric study of scientific publications to analyze the documents published in open access by the Insular Caribbean Region. The SCOPUS database (an Elsevier product) was used as a source of information. This database is one of the most used resources for research and evaluation of scientific activity. Over the last few years, it has become more established worldwide and currently offers a greater documental coverage for the Caribbean region, even more so than the Web of Science.

In order to recover the scientific documents, we have developed an advanced search strategy in the AFFILCOUNTRY field, which retrieves the country part of an author's address. With the support of Boolean operators, the countries that make up the Insular Caribbean Region and have scientific production identified in SCOPUS were searched by name:

AFFILCOUNTRY (Anguilla OR (“Antigua and Barbuda”) OR Aruba OR Bahamas OR Barbados OR (“Cayman Islands”) OR Cuba OR Curaçao OR Dominica OR (“Dominican Republic”) OR Grenada OR Guadeloupe OR Haiti OR Jamaica OR Martinique OR Montserrat OR (“Netherlands Antilles”) OR (“Puerto Rico”) OR (“Saint Barthélemy”) OR (“Saint Kitts and Nevis”) OR (“Saint Lucia”) OR (“Saint Vincent and the Grenadines”) OR (“Sint Maarten”) OR (“Trinidad and Tobago”) OR (“Turks and Caicos Islands”) OR (“Virgin Islands”))

Searches were executed between November and December 2022. We have searched all types of documents published by Insular Caribbean countries in all languages, during the period 2000–2020, to map their participation in OA scientific publishing. The decision of limiting our search to this timespan has been made to focus on the after period referring to the 3 major statements and declarations on the principles of Open Access: BOAI, Bethesda Statement and Berlin Declaration.

After data cleaning and normalization, the following bibliometric indicators were obtained: types of OA publications, growth of OA documents, most productive countries, languages and research areas.

Preliminary results and discussion

Types of OA publications

Approximately a one-fourth (26%) of the 85,489 documents produced by authors from the Insular Caribbean Region between the years 2000-2020 are published in open access. Regarding the route used to make documents available in open access, Figure 2 shows that most researchers (19%) opted for the green way, also known as self-archiving. This model allows an author to post a version of a paper in an institutional repository accessible for everyone from the internet. This version is not the final version which the journal publishes, it may be a preprint of the submitted manuscript before or after review. It means that green OA articles are supplied by the authors on a web site that is freely available without publisher mediation.

Figure 2. Percentage of publications by type of OA in the Insular Caribbean Region, 2000-2020.

Growth of OA documents

An analysis of the evolution of these publications over the last 20 years shows that from the beginning of this century the traditional model of science communication has undergone profound changes in the Insular Caribbean Region.

Figure 3 presents the percentage of documents published in open access with at least one author affiliated to the region. It increased from 10% (2277 publications) in 2000 to 45% (5787

publications) in 2020. It is worth noting the significant growth especially between 2004 and 2006. On the other hand, while the absolute number of publications signed by authors from the Insular Caribbean has been increasing at an average annual rate of 5%, the average increase in publications in all open access modalities for the same period in Scopus has grown by 13%.

Figure 3. Annual evolution of the number of publications and percentage of documents in OA. Insular Caribbean Region, 2000-2020.

Additionally, when we disaggregate the OA types by year of publication, Figure 4 demonstrates that the gold model (that makes the final version of the published article available for free at the time of publication) has been growing at an accelerated rate, especially since 2010.

Figure 4. Annual evolution of the number of publications by type of OA in the Insular Caribbean Region, 2000-2020.

This is mainly due to the collaborative work between editorial boards, academic journals and university libraries that develop university repositories and online journals portals. These policy initiatives are led by public universities and scientific organizations in the region, and are financed with public funds, without commercial intermediation. Examples of these initiatives

can be found in the creation of the Regional Online Information System for Scientific Journals of Latin America, the Caribbean, Spain and Portugal (Latindex), the Network of Scientific Journals of Latin America, the Caribbean, Spain and Portugal (RedALyC), the Ibero-American Network of Innovation and Scientific Knowledge (REDIB), the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), the Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO), among others, that operate as digital libraries and offer open access to the full text of journal articles published in the region. Such projects are particularly relevant for developing countries. They not only provide access to the scientific production for the institutions and researchers, but also promote the visibility and international recognition of the science produced in those countries.

Countries

The analysis by countries (table 1) shows that Cuba was the largest regional producer in OA, accounting for 32% of total production. It is the largest island in the Caribbean and one of the most influential countries in the sub-region. According Santin & Caregnato (2020) and Carvajal Tapia & Carvajal Rodríguez (2019), Cuba has a high production by regional standards and exceeds the largest nations in area and population in Latin America. It placing the country in an advantageous position in the dissemination of research results. Sensitization and training of authors about open access, adoption of institutional self-archiving policies, development of an infrastructure of digital open access repositories, and advice to editors of national scientific journals in topics related to intellectual property and Creative Commons licenses, are among the main actions proposed to increase access to and use of research results in the country (Casate-Fernández & Senso-Ruiz, 2017).

Table 1. Distribution of OA publications by country, Insular Caribbean Region, 2000-2020.

	Total number of documents	Number of OA documents	% Open Access documents in the country	% Open Access respect to the Insular Caribbean Region
Cuba	40569	7411	18.27%	32.74%
Puerto Rico	17285	6155	35.61%	27.19%
Trinidad and Tobago	7378	2001	27.12%	8.84%
Jamaica	7067	1964	27.79%	8.68%
Barbados	2445	858	35.09%	3.79%
Dominican Republic	2229	996	44.68%	4.40%
Grenada	2129	699	32.83%	3.09%
Guadeloupe	1598	557	34.86%	2.46%
Haiti	1414	831	58.77%	3.67%
Saint Kitts and Nevis	908	455	50.11%	2.01%

The second country with the most open access documents published in the Insular Caribbean Region is Puerto Rico (27%). It has the main public university system in the United States of America, as well the largest and most diverse academic offerings in the Caribbean region. The University of Puerto Rico (UPR) consists of eleven campuses and has approximately 58,000 students and 5,300 faculty members. In fact, Suárez-Balseiro et al. (2020) highlighted the participation of this institution in the economic development of Puerto Rico. Since April 2020, the UPR has had an Open Access Policy for research produced by members of the institution (University of Puerto Rico, 2020).

On the other hand, in terms of national-level efforts, we have observed that more than half of the publications produced by Haiti - the third largest country in the Caribbean by area - are available in OA, followed by Saint Kitts and Nevis (50%) and the Dominican Republic (44%). Due the fact that their scientific research and scholarly communication infrastructures are mainly publicly funded, the region has adopted OA as the main scholarly publishing model (Appel et al., 2018). The remaining countries, although contributing certain volumes of production, have moderate levels of OA publication.

Languages

In Scopus, English accounts for more documents than the other languages (Chung & Tsay, 2017). In the case of OA documents by the Insular Caribbean Region it is the same: the mostly are published in English (93.37%), followed by Spanish (7.40%). All other languages such as Portuguese, French, German, Russian, Turkish, Estonian and Japanese count for 1.37% only. A similar study carried out for the period 2005–2017 shows that 70.37% OA documents indexed by Web of Science database are published in English (Minniti et al., 2018).

Research areas

Regarding subject areas among the search results for OA related papers, practices are differently according to different disciplines (Appel et al., 2018). We found that Medicine documents dominate and account for the 41.55% of the sample in the Insular Caribbean Region. It is followed by Agricultural and Biological Sciences (14.67%), Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology (14.23%), Physics and Astronomy (10.61%), and Immunology and Microbiology (8.08%). A similar study for a large-scale confirmed that the proportion of OA is relatively high in biomedical research and math, while notably low in engineering, chemistry, and the humanities (Piwowar et al., 2018).

Preliminary conclusions

This study described open access uptake in the Insular Caribbean Region between 2000-2020 using SCOPUS. 26% of the 85,489 articles with Caribbean authors are published in OA, with green as most common (19%). The study also found that the percentage of documents published in OA increased from 10% in 2000 to 45% in 2020, and the gold model has been growing at an accelerated rate since 2010. Cuba and Puerto Rico are the largest user base, and health research having faster uptake.

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